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Introducing Process Simulation in Junior Level Chemical Engineering Courses Using a Problem Based Approach

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Abstract

Problem-based Learning (PBL) is an approach that challenges students to "learn how to learn," working in groups to seek solutions to real world problems. The process replicates the commonly used systemic approach to resolving problems or meeting challenges that are encountered in practice, and will help prepare students for their careers. In this respect, the intent is to begin the development of students toward expert level. Cognitive psychology [1] and naturalistic decision making communities have developed an extensive amount of literature documenting the differences between novice and expert performance. It is now an established notion that individuals learn by building on what they know. However, chemical engineering students often enter their junior year with various misconceptions, some with minimal knowledge of the domain and a minimum understanding of how the discipline is organized. Therefore, developing learning events, for these students (novices) require us to understand what the differences are between students and experts, which will enable the selection of appropriate instructional strategy [2]. In order to design training that will support this learning process, it is essential to define the two levels of proficiency and understand the differences between them.

Conference Key Areas: Classroom delivery, engineering domain knowledge, summative assessment, formative assessment, curriculum development

Keywords: Concept Inventory, engineering problem solving, conceptual learning, process simulation

INTRODUCTION

Leading organizations [3],[4] such as the American Society for Engineering Education; National Academy of Engineering [5], and President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology [6] have made a national pitch in favor of improvement in undergraduate science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) education. The envisioned improvements would be a vehicle to increase quality, and diversity of STEM graduates. However, such an outcome is unachievable without keen attention to the instructional practices of STEM faculty. Currently, as public institutions struggle with budgetary issues, and in many cases, underperformance based on metrics such as graduation rates, growing attention toward instructional practices of STEM faculty is encouraging the adoption of research-based teaching.

Problem Solving

It is an accepted notion in the engineering community that problem solving is central to engineering practice activities and is a key component of engineering training. In the spring 2016 semester a section of the chemical engineering junior-level separation process course was piloted to deliver new information in a workshop format in the first part of a week, then conduct process simulations in the second part of each week to validate results or explain discrepancies obtained through graphical or hand calculations. Each significant example calculation that accompanies a new topic area such as using the McCabe-Thiele Method to determine the number of theoretical stages in a given distillation process were subjected to this modified course delivery approach. In addition, students worked in groups of three or four on the simulations and were required to document their results in a structured report format, and submitted for grading as a mini-project. Formative assessment using Students Assessment of their Learning Gains (SALG) [7], resulted in 100% response rates with at least 67% of the class reporting moderate–great gain in understanding content, impact on their attitude, increase in their skills, integration of their learning and helpfulness of their class activities along with the benefit of citing their experience on their resumes. These formative assessments were conducted to ensure that the change in delivery from previous practices was not a source of distraction and will be continued as part of the course but not as the focus of the work being proposed here.

Instructor Reflection

Observation along with feedback from colleagues who have been teaching the course revealed that students have entered the process separations course with a substantial deficit in domain knowledge and an alarming amount of misconceptions about transport processes. In addition, it appears that students armed with current computational-able technology are deciding to abandon traditional problem solving techniques such as developing a process diagram, an abstract representation, containing all given

information prior to attempting to delve into deriving solutions. This approach usually lead to poor results and frustration. It is well established in the literature [1], that the quality of a problem representation influences the ease with which such a problem can be solved. Others have observed that physics experts organize their problem representations around abstract physics principles while novices tend to organize their representations and approaches around the problem surface features [8], [9]. According to some [10], concepts function as organizers, that is, they help us to differentiate between plants and animals or velocity and mass and momentum. Concepts allow us to categorize our physical surroundings and does have an impact on what we do with our categorized information. This means that understanding conceptual knowledge is a critical factor in the development of competence in engineering students and in practicing professionals [11], [12]. Indeed, the inability to recognize changes in process variables such as flowrates, temperature or pressure will ultimately lead to poor designs and sizing of operating equipment for use in processes involving energy exchanges, the consequence of which can be extremely costly in both economics and human lives.

AIM

In this work, we seek to use the process simulator as a means to refocus students on the concepts relevant to process separation. Process simulators by design contain several combinations of thermodynamic systems (packages) that capture the conceptual characteristics of real operating thermal and transport systems. For example, in a distillation process one (or students) must select a package that can predict the behavior of a given combination of chemical species under a specified set of operating conditions of temperature and pressure. The product distribution and accuracy of such a simulation forms the basis for the design and construction of industrial operating separation process systems. The thermal and transport concepts built into the thermodynamic packages are taught in prerequisite thermodynamic courses, however, course delivery time constraints substantially limit the amount of application-related practice in such prerequisite courses. Here, we seek to identify and repair conceptual weaknesses as they pertain to process separation. We plan to focus on those concepts exposed in thermodynamics relating to heat transfer, mass transfer, phase equilibria, and molecular diffusion all of which are considered difficult to understand. Misconceptions in these emergent processes could arise very early in science education, for example, in the study of blood circulatory system in an 8th grade biology class where a causal mechanism between the constituent components and the pattern in a non-direct process were underemphasized [13]. Indeed, if the identified misconceptions are longstanding, a corrective process employing a process simulator may prove to be an effective strategy given students' penchant for current computation-able technology, given that such misconceptions are still operational.

In a study conducted on undergraduate students' beliefs about engineering problem solving, five major categories were uncovered that are influential [14]: 1) The problem solving process, 2) The role of classroom problems, 3) The role of workplace problems, 4) Personal characteristics that affect problem solving and 5) The resources that assist problem solving. It has also been reported that students who preferred a classroom setting tended to conceptualize learning engineering as "testing" and "calculating and

practicing” while students who preferred a laboratory setting conceptualize learning engineering as “increasing one’s knowledge,” “applying,” “understanding,” and “seeing in a new way” [15]. Further, the conceptions of learning for science can be represented by seven categories [16]: “memorizing,” “testing,” “calculating,” “increasing knowledge,” “applying,” “understanding,” and “seeing in a new way,” can be further subdivided into two views of learning; a lower-level view and a high-level view. The conceptions consisting of “memorizing,” “testing,” and “calculating and practicing” are reproductive learning strategies and reflect a lower-level view of learning; while “applying,” “understanding, and” “seeing in a new way” are considered constructive learning strategies and reflect a high-level view of learning [16], [17].

Strategy

Recognizing that one approach to facilitating the capability to allow expertise to develop is to improve the level of domain knowledge and repair misconceptions of the incoming junior-level chemical engineering students entering the process separation course. Therefore, we are targeting their problem solving process to incorporate the strategies and techniques that practicing engineers are likely to use in their daily practice. Our approach will include categories 1, 2 and 5 as reported in [14] with the understanding that practicing (or real) engineers require a much broader problem-solving repertoire than any 4-year academic program can provide [18]. Indeed, real engineering experience will be acquired over the course of time following graduation, notwithstanding limited hands-on approaches that have been interjected through internships where available prior to graduation. We also seek to achieve the high-level view of learning: “applying,” “understanding, and” “seeing in a new way” [16], and [17] in our graduates as this skill will provide them a head start toward becoming an expert engineer.

METHODS

It is a widely studied notion that, people tend to retain overly favorable views of their abilities in intellectual and social domains [19]. This overestimation of ones abilities seem to be rooted in the lack of the metacognitive ability to realize ones’ own deficit. Apparently, the very skills that are required to evaluate competence in a domain are the exact ones lacking in the evaluator of others in that domain. There are established testing formats reported in the literature that can be adapted to determine which quartile display this metacognitive deficit [19], [20], and such instruments will be considered as an adjunct whose results may be useful in addressing longstanding misconceptions.

In addition, we will adopt results from past studies in chemical engineering education, for example [21], whose efforts focused on identifying important concepts in thermal and transport science that are difficult for engineering students to learn. In addition, we will consider and adapt approaches and results from others, such as in [22] that have already identified related thermodynamic and heat transfer concept areas along with accompanying common misconceptions with a different perspective.

Following the identification of the affected concepts in both thermodynamics and transport processes as they pertain to process separation, we plan to follow published

works such as in [23] to seek confirmation of the reported effectiveness of differentiated overt learning activities in our study. Specifically, we anticipate creating an environment that supports interactive and constructive activities.

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